

Open Science Hardware Practices and Potentialities for Africa:

A Rapid Literature Review

Authors: Abdoul kafid TOKO KOUTOGUI, Bolaji AKOREDE, Abdulwasiu TIAMIYU, Suleiman ABDULSALAM

Mohammed VI Polytechnic University, School of Collective Intelligence

Corresponding author: Abdoul Kafid TOKO KOUTOGUI Email: abdoukafid.toko@um6p.ma

Introduction

Africa must face several challenges to promote the well-being of a growing population in a global context with many constraints, such as climate change. To achieve a robust infrastructure to solve problems in the continent, several start-up strategies in various domains are being tested by the African Governments, who need to consider each solutions' sustainability. Economic and social development are intimately linked to scientific and technological progress. Given these challenges, Africa needs to accelerate its capacity for innovation through scientific progress. A **complex development problem** that requires efforts by local, national, and international stakeholders. Studies such as those by Ahenkan and OseiKojo (2014) raise that despite public policy efforts on the continent, there seems to be deep scepticism about Africa's ability to address issues related to levels of poverty and food insecurity to achieve Sustainable Development Goals.¹

Despite the various economic issues like hyperinflation, Sub-Saharan African countries are observing economic growth. Financial development does not have the same effects as technology and science growth when the focus is on sustainability. Mesagan et al. (2023) reveal through a study that financial development has a positive but insignificant long-term influence on Africa's development, while the short-term effect is negative but significant. The growth of production in the long term

¹ Ahenkan et Osei-Kojo, « Achieving sustainable development in Africa: Progress, challenges and prospects ».

is stimulated by the growth of technological progress, even if its effect is not significant in the short term.²

It is thus important to be able to make innovation evolve for technological progress through science. Innovation and wealth creation are linked, as studies like Ulku's 2004 report (based on 20 OECD and 10 Non-OECD countries) suggest a positive relationship between GDPs per capita and innovation.³ Doing scientific research and innovation with advanced skills in better conditions has implications for the ability to change the socio-economic situation of countries. A positive relationship⁴ has been established between high-skill services and African economic development (Baccini et al., 2023).

In the context of the unavailability of resources (financial, human, and material), and the need to advance innovation, it is necessary to identify the right strategy to share these resources in the most effective way to advance research and innovation.

Information is at the heart of all human actions, and movements with a philosophy of openness like Open Science Hardware (OSH) favor the emergence of community for an adequate sharing of information, which can catalyse change. The trust that arises between individuals within these communities is what Maria T. (2015) describes as social capital. This capital is fundamental for innovation activities, according to the author, because it facilitates cooperation and information sharing between economic agents. How do we evolve movements with an open philosophy to develop social capital and drive innovation for the common good in Africa? The purpose of this rapid literature review is to identify practices already documented in the specific field of open science hardware in Africa. This will allow us to analyze the potential of this movement to accompany the achievement of sustainable development goals through an open science for the common good.

² Mesagan, Vo, et Emmanuel, « The Technological Role in the Growth-Enhancing Financial Development ».

³ Ulku, « R&D, Innovation, and Economic Growth ».

⁴ Baccini et al., « Services, Jobs, and Economic Development in Africa ».

⁵ Roscoe, Vieira, et Grzybovski, « Chapter 9 ».

Literature review of the selected articles

Through a rapid review of the literature, we identify preconditions and challenges hindering open science's evolution in Africa. It is also an analysis of past practices in more advanced regions to identify the potential of this movement for Africa. This review also allows us to foresight on the potentialities of the movement for developing countries.

Open hardware for common good and science development (1)

The development of open hardware for specific tasks in science and society is a matter of public utility to solve problems. For instance, scientific work is essential for all to get clean water. In Africa 411 million citizens lack safe water (« 2023 Africa Sustainable Development Report », s. d.), access to clean water is a luxury for these communities. Thinking deeply about cost efficient open-source solutions is an alternative that Wijnen et al. (2014) present to strengthen actions for water access.⁵ In their case study, Wijnen et al. present a methodology that allows them to obtain **water quality analysis equipment with good accuracy** at a cost that is 7.5 to 15 times lower than the tools available on the market. The researchers conclude that open-source hardware development is a promising alternative for the equipment needed to perform water quality measurements in developed and developing regions.

OSH for knowledge transfer (3)

The strategy of facilitating access to hardware for researchers is an objective that can be achieved through the Open Hardware movement by facilitating the transfer of knowledge to scientific environments characterized by economic and infrastructural constraints. Do-it-yourself (make your own) technologies facilitate this movement of knowledge and have great potential through this information sharing and local production, according to Wenzel (2023)⁶. This knowledge transfer approach is further raised by Ahluwalia et al. (2015) in a study that highlights open biomedical engineering education in Africa⁷. These researchers present the situation of ignoring

⁵ Wijnen, Anzalone, et Pearce, « Open-source mobile water quality testing platform ».

⁶ Wenzel, « Global technology access in biolabs -- from DIY trend to an open source transformation ».

⁷ Ahluwalia et al., « Open Biomedical Engineering education in Africa ».

the potential of web-based teaching resources, the expansion of open-source software, hardware, and rapid prototyping (new technologies to produce precision components directly from Computer-Aided Design models). This research demonstrates how the introduction of open science concepts through the education of biomedical engineering students and rapid prototyping facilitates early development and self-sufficiency in health care. The introduction of this philosophy in three universities (with limited facilities) has resulted in an enthusiastic response from students (key players in the development of scientific work in Africa) and teachers. This same effect observed in Africa is like what Cota et al. (2020) demonstrate in an argument for the viability of the OSH model for entrepreneurship and technological innovation in the academic environment in Brazil⁸. The study shows that these models are still relevant in achieving their benefits for socio-economic innovation in health and education.

OSH for a sustainable R&D and strong networking for Africa Scientist

Whether in Africa or South America, open-source technologies are of great use in fundamental areas such as medical practice (Chavez & Kovarik, 2019) in developing countries.⁹ More specifically, research for genomic medicine applications, according to (Hetu et al., 2019) has great potential to improve the health care of the population in low- and middle-income countries.¹⁰ To enable these countries to keep up with the pace of technological development in high-income nations, capacity building for the participation of the field in these developing countries in international initiatives is essential. These researchers have tested this through a pilot study on four international (involving Africa) Open Science genomics projects. The results show that these types of projects contribute to capacity building in genomics in developing countries. Still, their role in potentially redistributing the benefits of research to the populations of these countries is mixed due to limited infrastructure, underrepresentation in studies, restrictive intellectual property policies, and unequal access to decision-making roles. Thus, they suggest the deployment of initiatives likely to facilitate the participation of researchers from developing countries in the

⁸ Cota et al., « Open-source hardware as a model of technological innovation and academic entrepreneurship ».

⁹ Chavez et Kovarik, « Open Source Technology for Medical Practice in Developing Countries ».

¹⁰ Hetu, Koutouki, et Joly, « Genomics for All ».

international genomics research community, but above all to accelerate capacity building in the development of concrete projects useful to the communities such as agricultural development.

OSH for local solutions innovation and education in developing countries (7)

This connection between open science initiatives and community development was the subject of a study by Ausareny et al. (2014), who worked on the use of Open-Source Hardware (OSHW) as a tool for communicating emerging scientific and technical knowledge through craft. The researchers, therefore, focused on traditional crafts widely employed in the Global South. The researchers used traditional wayang kulit theatre as a model for building microfluidic (Science of fluid handling systems) interfaces, which communicate emerging scientific issues to the public while testing the possibilities of DIY microfluidics¹¹. This human-centered approach was also tested (Webb et al., 2019) with laboratory hackathons to explore an alternative way to address the shortage of laboratory equipment in Africa for science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) practice and education¹². The researchers drew on the open hardware movement to pilot lab hackathons through simple and fun work sessions to challenge students to design frugal (contextually appropriate) and reproducible lab equipment. The case study, with the **LabHackathon** model, shows that this approach combining education allows K-12 learners to emerge as makers who build with basic means the tools necessary to exercise science at the grassroots. This approach has also been tested in Brazil by (R. Brazil, 2018) to show that open science material could facilitate the obtaining and maintenance of high-technology equipment associated with modern laboratories¹³. In the hospital setting, Farré et al. (2022) raises the possibility that in low-income countries, open hardware can address the shortage of medical devices for low-income patients with chronic respiratory diseases. Access to medical devices helps practice of research and medical education in his countries¹⁴. In this same

¹¹ Ausareny et al., « Open source hardware (OSHW) supporting interaction between traditional crafts and emergent science ».

¹² Webb et al., « Lab Hackathons to Overcome Laboratory Equipment Shortages in Africa ».

¹³ Brazil, « Open-Science Hardware in the Developing World ».

¹⁴ Farré et al., « Open-Source Hardware May Address the Shortage in Medical Devices for Patients with Low-Income and Chronic Respiratory Diseases in Low-Resource Countries ».

vein, Salido et al. (2022) conducted a review of low-cost microscopes for open science, and tools like Foldscope (PFM-BL) and OpenFlexure (AMM-WSI-) stand out for their significant impact on science learning and the community-created around them. The objective is to facilitate the development of research in biological sciences in institutions with limited resources, as well as the diagnosis of diseases and screening of large populations in developing countries and training in educational contexts requiring high equipment availability and a low replacement cost¹⁵.

Such initiatives are what the Global Open Science Hardware (GOSH) movement is about—bringing together actors from academia, education, the private sector, and civil society across different countries. Arancio (2021) examines this movement's emergence and key characteristics from a transition theory and grassroots innovation movement framework. The authors show that this movement will allow for a better understanding of niche development in the case of transitions to more plural and democratic socio-technical systems¹⁶. It is in this spirit of broadening the scope of Open Science Hardware within research, NGO (Non-governmental organizations) initiatives, and education that Dosemagen et al. present the "Gathering for Open Science Hardware" organized in 2016, as a way to break down the silos and clusters created by geographical barriers¹⁷. A gathering that also had a great diversity of participation, with actors coming from Africa to prime a global community.

Africa OSH development challenges and strategy to undertake with other developing countries for change (3)

Africa is not alone in this journey of catching up in scientific efforts, it is important to have a working group to think about research strategy in the region. According to Onie (2020), scientific research is relatively new in many countries in Asia, Africa, and Latin America. Young scientists in these regions are striving to build open science practices from the ground up. The goal of the scientific communities in these regions would be to integrate these principles progressively with the development of their work as their needs differ from those of advanced research systems, so these scientists should collaboratively strive to design their systems rather than modify and

¹⁵ Salido et al., « A Review on Low-Cost Microscopes for Open Science ».

¹⁶ Arancio, « Opening Up The Tools For Doing Science ».

¹⁷ Dosemagen, Liboiron, et Molloy, « Gathering for Open Science Hardware 2016 ».

shape established ones¹⁸. Onie therefore, emphasizes the need to amplify work that can **think of systems and frameworks for the development of Open Science Hardware** that fit the needs of the moment in Africa and across the developing world. An example of this is the case of African scientists who rely on Open Science Hardware through DIY activities to better equip their laboratories: the case of the development of a local high-impact device called Actifield (a device that quantifies animal activity) by Victor Kumbol (a master's student in neuroscience) in Ghana (Tsanni, 2020)¹⁹.

Examples like the one highlighted by Tsanni need to be replicated across the continent, given its size and need. This is why a study by (Mwelwa et al., 2020) argues for boosting national science systems and their role in supporting the public and private and public sectors²⁰. The study also presents the **complexity of social and economic challenges** and the lack of an adequate digital infrastructure. It also highlights the **scientific system that does not promote good interconnection between African actors** who operate independently of each other. A situation that can be partly explained by Africa's linguistic diversity (English, French, Portuguese, Spanish, and indigenous languages). Nevertheless, the potential of a well-developed open science system in Africa is to develop and enhance collaborations and partnerships between local actors to work towards addressing societal challenges through accelerated innovation and development.

Methods and tools

The overall methodology used in this Rapid Literature Review is based on the approach described by Sacré et al ²¹ but also (Smela et al. 2023)²². This approach allows us to understand several set of review designs.

¹⁸ Onie, « Redesign Open Science for Asia, Africa and Latin America ».

¹⁹ Tsanni, « African Scientists Leverage Open Hardware ».

²⁰ Mwelwa et al., « Developing Open Science in Africa ».

²¹ Sacré, Lafontaine, et Toczek, « Comprendre et concevoir des revues systématiques de la littérature en sciences de l'éducation et de la formation ».

²² Beata Smela et al., « Rapid Literature Review: Definition and Methodology ».

Search strategy

The four collaborators agreed on a list of 12 keywords to guide the search for relevant articles. These keywords were selected to cover various aspects of the topic and include:

- Open science hardware Africa
- Open science hardware in developing countries
- Open science hardware practices in Africa
- Open science hardware practices in developing countries
- Open science hardware potentialities Africa
- Open science hardware potentialities in developing countries
- Open hardware communities in Africa
- Open hardware communities in developing countries
- Open designs Africa
- Open designs in developing countries
- Modern digital fabrication Africa
- Modern digital fabrication in developing countries

The initial search for articles was conducted using major academic databases, including: Cairn e-Library, ScienceDirect, Web of Science, ProQuest, Scopus and SpringerLink. However, the query results from these databases did not yield content specifically relevant to open science hardware. This is due to the lack of an academic search engine specific to the Open Science Hardware theme.

So an alternative search strategy has been adopted to refine the search. The team employed Google Scholar and used Elicit (<https://elicit.com>)²³, a research assistant tool, to simultaneously query multiple databases using the term "Open Science Hardware in Africa". This approach helped identify an initial list of articles.

Inclusion Criteria

We considered articles dealing with Open-science Hardware in Africa and developing countries in the global south. Some articles dealing globally with open science policies in Africa with implications for open hardware were also considered.

²³ Whitfield et Hofmann, « Elicit ».

We collected articles in English and French (the two languages spoken by the researchers involved).

Screening and selection of studies

The metadata of the collected articles was exported from Zotero, a citation management tool, and imported into Covidence²⁴. This allows us to first identify and eliminate with efficiency the probable duplication of and eliminate the probable duplication of studies. The tool allows us to reach a consensus on the choice of studies to retain based on the criteria previously defined. Our choice of Covidence also lies in the fact that it allows us to keep track of the statistical data on this screening and selection stage, the metrics necessary to report on the review, and demonstrate the transparency of the process. Thus, the filtering of references through (title, abstract, and full text of articles), the creation and filling of data extraction forms, and the design of risk of bias tables were done with a digital tool.

Based on the research objectives, and the overall understanding of the previous readings, we proceeded to identify the relevant data for the systematic review through a screening of the titles and abstracts and then the full text of the included articles.

The main results of the selected studies were summarized in the literature review provided earlier in the chapter. The following figure 1 presents a flow chart of the steps:

²⁴ Goulas, « How Can I Cite Covidence? »

Figure 1: Screening and selection of articles for rapid review

Synthesis methods

For the synthesis, we use our data extraction to create a simple descriptive statistic, and then we use qualitative analysis to categorize (based on the subject) the articles used in the synthesis into thematic patterns.

Results

Overview

Following the different selections and extractions of the data (see Figure 1), 19 articles were found to be relevant. These scientific works are rather recent, as they are less than 10 years old. However, the number of scientific publications related to open science hardware in African and developing countries has been growing especially since 2020. This can be explained by the great movements and efforts to advance the movement in Africa but also explain the need for research and development on the continent. Only 36.8% of the paper focuses only on Africa's context or use cases with the other on the global south.

Analysis

Overall, 52.63% of the papers focus on **policy issues for Open Science Hardware**; none of the studies are purely experimental, and only one is an empirical study. The studies in the field are therefore much more about case studies. Only 42.11% of the articles discuss how to practically use OSH. Also, 36.84% of the paper gives us direct information about the potentiality of OSH for Africa.

Figure 2. OSH papers clustering

Qualitative analysis allows us to classify the studies into five categories addressing different aspects that enable us to understand the practices and initiatives of Open Science Hardware in Africa and also to appreciate its potential.

The first category of articles in this review reminds us how essential the development of Open Hardware is for solving the fundamental science and society problems in Africa. The second category of articles is composed of three studies, including the one by Wenzel that appeared in 2023, which discusses the development of Open Science as a means of facilitating knowledge transfer between regions around the world for the emergence of innovation, entrepreneurship initiatives, and to facilitate an improvement in the quality of STEM education for youth.²⁵

The third category of articles written by Chavez, Kovarik, and Hetu, all published in 2019, provides an understanding of the potential of Open Science Hardware in capacity building for African researchers to engage in new R&D for innovation to solve societal problems related to health, etc. It is also a way to connect African

²⁵ Wenzel, « Global technology access in biolabs -- from DIY trend to an open source transformation ».

researchers to global communities to amplify the impact of projects and technological advances.²⁶

The fourth category, with seven articles, allows us to understand the development of the OSH as a movement promoting innovation and involving diverse stakeholders in the effort to find local solutions to the continent's challenges. With the introduction of global initiatives that involve Africa in the dynamics of sustainable change. The last category is composed of three studies that analyze the challenges related to the development of the OSH movement in Africa and the possibilities of collective action strategies between African countries and their peers in Asia and Latin America for the sustainable development of projects in the field.

The Open Science Hardware movement: a common breeding ground for public innovation in Africa

The socio-economic transformation in Africa is a challenge that requires the reproduction and creation of many technological tools. As well as large-scale tools production to improve health, agriculture, and industry given the continued growth of the population. All of this can only be achieved through the development of innovation and value creation within these countries.

The development of innovation and all related ecosystems can only be effective through the advancement of knowledge and science. Making the implementation of strategies to democratize the practice of science an urgent priority in Africa. How can this dynamic be initiated in a context where the number of professionals involved in the design of new knowledge, new products, new processes, new methods, or new systems is limited? According to the data compiled by Our World in Data on the "Number of R&D researchers per million inhabitants" database, we can see those countries like Morocco and Tunisia, which have the most researchers, have 1081 and 1584 per million, respectively, and if we go to countries like South Africa (473) and Ghana (87) in the sub-Saharan zone, this number drops considerably²⁷. The supply of higher education is neither quantitatively nor qualitatively strong enough to meet the training needs for the rapid transformation of the continent. The complexity

²⁶ Chavez et Kovarik, « Open Source Technology for Medical Practice in Developing Countries ».

²⁷ « Number of R&D researchers per million people ».

of this context calls for creative action to facilitate access to learning and the exercise of the scientific profession for innovation in all fields.

This is where the open science movement for hardware, software, and documentation comes in. It removes entry barriers by making the tools and methods for doing science accessible to all. It facilitates frugal innovation in the practice of science, as every aspiring scientist regardless of geographical location can access prototypes, documents, and other resources. Communities like the open science hardware community in Africa offer these possibilities but give something even more important: the ability for African researchers/innovators to grow their global networks. A professional networking dynamic that facilitates the transfer of knowledge and experience between different regions of the world. This facilitates the pooling of innovation efforts and resources in a global setting. And with the challenges of sustainability worldwide, the open science hardware movement will play a key role in helping to achieve SDG 9, co-design and build resilient infrastructures, and the emergence of inclusive industrialization underpinned by collaborative innovation.

This outlook is only possible through the development of a long-term transformation strategy to train and nurture innovation champions supported by the research and fertility of free intellectual production, motivated by the designing human-centred solutions to enhance population well-being. Industry groups like OCP Morocco can also support the operation of communities to bring out collective creativity through science, which would be useful for innovation, which is also a guarantee of growth for companies, to create more value and employment in countries.

As we have noted from the results of this review, the articles tackling the subject of open science hardware in Africa document practical STEM education use cases, and community of practice development initiatives by innovators and passionate scientists. In the African context, the movement's potential is enormous, but it needs to take a holistic approach and be intimately linked to education. With a young population of secondary school and university age, it's timely to identify a mechanism for educating and transforming young people in school into open-science innovators.

The initiatives promoted by communities such as Africa Open Science Hardware are models that need to be accelerated and replicated on a large scale to satisfy the need for transformation across the continent. This is why we believe that studies on

the socio-economic and policy aspects of the movement need to be multiplied to help understand the mechanisms of rapid development. Using randomized controlled trial (RCT) research programs can help to rapidly identify the best strategies, document them scientifically, and advocate for transformation in education administration and policy.

Bibliography

- Ahenkan, Albert, et Alex Osei-Kojo. « Achieving sustainable development in Africa: Progress, challenges and prospects », 2014.
- Ahluwalia, Arti, Daniel Atwine, Carmelo De Maria, Charles Ibingira, Emmauel Kipkorir, Fasil Kiros, June Madete, et al. « Open Biomedical Engineering education in Africa ». In *2015 37th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC)*, 3687-90, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EMBC.2015.7319193>.
- Arancio, Julieta Cecilia. « Opening Up The Tools For Doing Science: The Case Of The Global Open Science Hardware Movement ». *International Journal of*

- Engineering, Social Justice, and Peace* 8, n° 2 (18 octobre 2021): 1-27.
<https://doi.org/10.24908/ijesjp.v8i2.13997>.
- . « Opening Up The Tools For Doing Science: The Case Of The Global Open Science Hardware Movement ». *International Journal of Engineering, Social Justice, and Peace* 8, n° 2 (18 octobre 2021): 1-27.
<https://doi.org/10.24908/ijesjp.v8i2.13997>.
- . « Opening Up The Tools For Doing Science: The Case Of The Global Open Science Hardware Movement ». *International Journal of Engineering, Social Justice, and Peace* 8, n° 2 (18 octobre 2021): 1-27.
<https://doi.org/10.24908/ijesjp.v8i2.13997>.
- Ausareny, Justyna, Denisa Kera, Stefania Druga, et Yair Reshef. « Open source hardware (OSHW) supporting interaction between traditional crafts and emergent science: wayang kulit over microfluidic interfaces ». In *SIGGRAPH Asia 2014 Designing Tools For Crafting Interactive Artifacts*, 1-4. SA '14. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2014.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/2668947.2668955>.
- Baccini, Leonardo, Matteo Fiorini, Bernard Hoekman, et Marco Sanfilippo. « Services, Jobs, and Economic Development in Africa ». *The World Bank Research Observer* 38, n° 1 (1 février 2023): 147-78.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/wbro/lkac006>.
- Brazil, Rachel. « Open-Science Hardware in the Developing World ». *Physics World* 31, n° 8 (août 2018): 30. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2058-7058/31/8/34>.
- Chavez, Afton, et Carrie Kovarik. « Open Source Technology for Medical Practice in Developing Countries ». In *Healthcare Policy and Reform: Concepts, Methodologies, Tools, and Applications*, 885-911. IGI Global, 2019.
<https://www.igi-global.com/chapter/open-source-technology-for-medical-practice-in-developing-countries/www.igi-global.com/chapter/open-source-technology-for-medical-practice-in-developing-countries/209161>.
- Chiwere, Elisha R. T., et Lara Skelly. « Open Science in Africa: What policymakers should consider ». *Frontiers in Research Metrics and Analytics* 7 (2022). <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/frma.2022.950139>.

- Cota, Vinícius Rosa, Cleiton Lopes Aguiar, Bezamat de Souza Neto, et Miguel Benegas. « Open-source hardware as a model of technological innovation and academic entrepreneurship: The Brazilian landscape ». *Innovation & Management Review* 17, n° 2 (1 janvier 2020): 177-95.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/INMR-06-2018-0036>.
- Dosemagen, Shannon, Max Liboiron, et Jenny Molloy. « Gathering for Open Science Hardware 2016 ». *Journal of Open Hardware* 1, n° 1 (25 avril 2017).
<https://doi.org/10.5334/joh.5>.
- Farré, Ramon, David Gozal, Viet-Nhung Nguyen, Joshua M. Pearce, et Anh Tuan Dinh-Xuan. « Open-Source Hardware May Address the Shortage in Medical Devices for Patients with Low-Income and Chronic Respiratory Diseases in Low-Resource Countries ». *Journal of Personalized Medicine* 12, n° 9 (septembre 2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390/jpm12091498>.
- . « Open-Source Hardware May Address the Shortage in Medical Devices for Patients with Low-Income and Chronic Respiratory Diseases in Low-Resource Countries ». *Journal of Personalized Medicine* 12, n° 9 (13 septembre 2022): 1498. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jpm12091498>.
- « Frontiers | Genomics for All: International Open Science Genomics Projects and Capacity Building in the Developing World ». Consulté le 26 avril 2023.
<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fgene.2019.00095/full>.
- Goulas, Giorgia. « How Can I Cite Covidence? », 28 juin 2022.
<https://support.covidence.org/help/how-can-i-cite-covidence>.
- Hetu, Martin, Konstantia Koutouki, et Yann Joly. « Genomics for All: International Open Science Genomics Projects and Capacity Building in the Developing World ». *Frontiers in Genetics* 10 (15 février 2019).
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fgene.2019.00095>.
- « IGI Global ». Consulté le 26 avril 2023.
<https://www.igi-global.com/gateway/chapter/www.igi-global.com/gateway/chapter/209161>.
- Juju, Denabo, Gideon Baffoe, Rodolfo Dam Lam, Alice Karanja, Merle Naidoo, Abubakari Ahmed, Marcin Pawel Jarzebski, et al. « Sustainability Challenges in Sub-Saharan Africa in the Context of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) ». In *Sustainability Challenges in Sub-Saharan*

Africa I: Continental Perspectives and Insights from Western and Central Africa, édité par Alexandros Gasparatos, Abubakari Ahmed, Merle Naidoo, Alice Karanja, Kensuke Fukushi, Osamu Saito, et Kazuhiko Takeuchi, 3-50. Singapore: Springer, 2020. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-4458-3_1.

Mesagan, Ekundayo Peter, Xuan Vinh Vo, et Precious Muhammed Emmanuel. « The Technological Role in the Growth-Enhancing Financial Development: Evidence from African Nations ». *Economic Change and Restructuring* 56, n° 1 (1 février 2023): 657-80. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10644-022-09442-z>.

Mwelwa, Joseph, Geoffrey Boulton, Joseph Muliari Wafula, et Cheikh Loucoubar. « Developing Open Science in Africa: Barriers, Solutions and Opportunities ». *Data Science Journal* 19, n° 1 (5 août 2020): 31. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-031>.

OCP Group. « The OCP Group Launches Its Open Innovation Platform “The Next Seed” ». Consulté le 3 décembre 2024. <http://www.ocpgroup.ma/press-release-article/ocp-group-launches-its-open-innovation-platform-next-seed>.

Okafor, Izuchukwu Azuka, Smart Ikechukwu Mbagwu, Terkuma Chia, Zuwati Hasim, Echezona Ejike Udokanma, et Karthik Chandran. « Institutionalizing Open Science in Africa: Limitations and Prospects ». *Frontiers in Research Metrics and Analytics* 7 (2022). <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/frma.2022.855198>.

Onie, Sandersan. « Redesign Open Science for Asia, Africa and Latin America ». *Nature* 587, n° 7832 (novembre 2020): 35-37. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-03052-3>.

« OSDG | Sustainable Development Goals for your input | OSDG.ai ». Consulté le 24 juin 2024. <https://osdg.ai/osdg?token=QGXc4Juq8Gz9ciDPs&type=PDF&outcome=successful>.

Our World in Data. « Number of R&D researchers per million people ». Consulté le 23 juin 2024. <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/researchers-in-rd-per-million-people>.

Our World in Data. « Number of R&D researchers per million people ». Consulté le 24 juin 2024.

<https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/researchers-in-rd-per-million-people>.

Pukelis, Lukas, Nuria Bautista-Puig, Gustė Statulevičiūtė, Vilius Stančiauskas, Gokhan Dikmener, et Dina Akyzbekova. « OSDG 2.0: a multilingual tool for classifying text data by UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) ». arXiv, 21 novembre 2022. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2211.11252>.

Roscoe, Maria Teresa, Adriane Vieira, et Denize Grzybovski. « Chapter 9: Family Social Capital, Transgenerational Learning and Transgenerational Entrepreneurship », 2015.

<https://www.elgaronline.com/edcollchap/edcoll/9781784717865/9781784717865.00018.xml>.

Sacré, Margault, Dominique Lafontaine, et Marie-Christine Toczek. « Comprendre et concevoir des revues systématiques de la littérature en sciences de l'éducation et de la formation ». *Nouveaux cahiers de la recherche en éducation* 23, n° 2 (2021): 1-27.

<https://doi.org/10.7202/1085361ar>.

Salido, Jesus, Gloria Bueno, Jesus Ruiz-Santaquiteria, et Gabriel Cristobal. « A Review on Low-Cost Microscopes for Open Science ». *Microscopy Research and Technique* 85, n° 10 (2022): 3270-83.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/jemt.24200>.

Smela, Beata, Mondher Toumi, Karolina Świerk, Clement Francois, Małgorzata Biernikiewicz, Emilie Clay, et Laurent Boyer. « Rapid Literature Review: Definition and Methodology ». *Journal of Market Access & Health Policy* 11, n° 1 (janvier 2023): 2241234.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/20016689.2023.2241234>.

Thompson, Maria. « Social Capital, Innovation and Economic Growth ». *Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Economics* 73 (1 avril 2018): 46-52.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socec.2018.01.005>.

Tsanni, Abdullahi. « African Scientists Leverage Open Hardware ». *Nature* 582, n° 7810 (1 juin 2020): 138-138. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-01606-z>.

Ulku, Hulya. « R&D, Innovation, and Economic Growth: An Empirical Analysis », 1 septembre 2004. <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=879010>.

- UNDP. « 2023 Africa Sustainable Development Report ». Consulté le 28 novembre 2024.
<https://www.undp.org/africa/publications/2023-africa-sustainable-development-report>.
- Webb, Helena, Jason R.C. Nurse, Louise Bezuidenhout, et Marina Jirotko. « Lab Hackathons to Overcome Laboratory Equipment Shortages in Africa: Opportunities and Challenges ». In *Extended Abstracts of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 1-8. CHI EA '19. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2019.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3290607.3299063>.
- Wenzel, Tobias. « Global technology access in biolabs -- from DIY trend to an open source transformation ». *PLOS Biology* 21, n° 1 (17 janvier 2023): e3001931. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3001931>.
- Whitfield, Sharon, et Melissa A. Hofmann. « Elicit: AI literature review research assistant ». *Public Services Quarterly* 19, n° 3 (3 juillet 2023): 201-7.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15228959.2023.2224125>.
- Wijnen, Bas, G. C. Anzalone, et Joshua M. Pearce. « Open-source mobile water quality testing platform ». *Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development* 4, n° 3 (9 mai 2014): 532-37.
<https://doi.org/10.2166/washdev.2014.137>.